

Impact of Climate Change on Ginger Production and Adaptation Strategies among Farmers in Southern parts of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Marajos Alkali

Department of Agricultural Education, College of Education Gidan Waya, Kafanchan, Kaduna state

Email address: josmoroa076@gmail.com

Abstract

This study sought to investigate the impact of climate change on ginger production and adaptation strategies among farmers in southern parts of Kaduna state. The descriptive research design was adopted. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The population for the study was 36,545 consisting of 36,515 ginger farmers and 30 Extension Agents (E.As). structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The instrument was face validated by five experts. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. Mean, Standard deviation and t-test statistic were used for data analysis. Results of the study indicated that some of the impacts of climate change on ginger production in the area include delayed onset and early cessation of rain, emergence of pests and diseases, reduction in yield among others. Findings further indicated that in order to survive the current changing weather condition with its attendant effect, ginger farmers employ the following as adaptation strategies: cover cropping, use of organic manure, mulching, protection of water shed, planting resistant and early maturing varieties, and mixed farming practices among others. Provision of early weather information among others will help farmers navigate the adverse effects of climate change.

Key words: impact, climate, production, adaptation, strategies, farmer

Introduction

Crop farming is the major occupation and important source of livelihood to the rural majority in most developing countries of Africa including Nigeria. It serves as a source of food for humans, feed for livestock, income to the farming households, marketers and processors of agricultural products and revenue to government (Alkali and Joyce, 2020) and believed to be the backbone of Nigeria's economy with about 70% farmers getting involved in one form of crop production activity or the other (Alkali and Kabirat, 2013). At both the local and macro levels, crop production is positioned to have a multiplier effect on any country's quest for socioeconomic

and industrial development (Oluwaseyi, 2017). One of the important crops cultivated by farmers in Nigeria and especially in southern part of Kaduna State is ginger.

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) is an herbaceous perennial plant belonging to the order scitamineae and a member of the family zingiberaceae. It is a root crop and a typical herb extensively grown across the world for its underground stem or rhizome. The importance of ginger production in improving human life has been noted and documented. It is one among the world's most popular spices and a condiment that is used to flavor meals such as sauces, deserts, cookies and drinks. Ginger contains a good percentage of essential oils which are extracted and used in confectionary, cosmetics, food processing, and medicine among other things. Oils extracted from ginger, specifically gingerols, have antibacterial, analgesic, sedative, and antipyretic properties. Ginger is also a multipurpose herb that can help in colds, flu, headache, and sore throats. Stressing the economic gains of ginger production, the Nigeria Export Promotion Commission (NEPC) in its Zero Oil plan had identified ginger as one of the strategic products with financial value capable of replacing oil (Ifeanyi, 2023). Olaghere, et al (2022) posited that the several uses of ginger have made it a very high sought-after crop.

The potentials of ginger production for economic development and poverty reduction through creation and expansion of employment opportunities and distribution of income in any nation cannot be over stressed especially in the study area with a large expanse of cultivable farms and favorable climatic conditions. Unfortunately, however, in spite of the potential of ginger production in the country and southern parts of Kaduna State, this spice sub-sector remains grossly under exploited with average yields estimated at about 5-12 tones per hectare. But more disturbing is the fact that a survey study reported by Sodangi (2020) showed low yields of ginger farms in Southern parts of Kaduna state attributable to a number of factors including poor soil fertility, shortage of improved cultivars, and lack of adoption of improved technologies. Others could be weather related such as late onset and early cessation of rainfall occasioned by climate change.

Climate change is the variation in the statistical distribution of average weather conditions in an area over a period of time. It is known to have direct and /or indirect effect on agricultural production especially crop production including ginger. Climate change has been a global issue affecting various agricultural production processes, including producers; their return to production as well as general family livelihood. Not only that, climate change is currently posing an existential

threat the world over through its effects in agriculture especially crop production. This is because of the sensitivity of crops to weather extreme events such as flowing, drought and rising temperature (Alkali and Joyce, 2020). Extreme weather events devastate farm lands and can lead to crop failure especially in Nigerian agriculture that is majorly rain fed resulting in increased hunger, and poverty. Hence, it can rightly be said that climate change constitutes a very serious threat to the realization of the United Nation's (UN) Sustainable Development Goals 1 and 2 of ending poverty and hunger for all persons.

Agriculture in the area of study is mostly rain fed, hence, changes in rainfall pattern have greatly affected crop farming including ginger. Farmers in the area have been complaining of crop failure arising from climate variability particularly delayed onset and early cessation of rains, flooding and emergence of pests and disease that were hitherto alien to the area. This was corroborated by Ifeanyi (2023) who decried that ginger production in Nigeria is being threatened as a result of the emergence of a strange disease suspected to be a fungal infection in southern parts of Kaduna. Ifeanyi stated that the infection has caused a general decline in ginger production and downturn in profit for ginger farmers in the country. As a result of this disease, the source added, Nigerian ginger export dropped to 30% of its previous years whereas farmers account for about 10-30 million naira in losses. Nigerian senate, in one of its plenaries, decried the huge economic loss recorded by ginger farmers in the area and expressed concern about the public health risk of this deadly disease because it has been shown that organisms that affect plants could develop some sort of host jumping through mutation and infect humans.

There is paucity of empirical studies on impact of climate change on ginger production and adaptation strategies among farmers in southern part of Kaduna state. Most previous studies on ginger production in the area have centered on constraints to efficient ginger production, factors affecting adoption of improved production among others. This study is therefore meant to fill this research gap by investigating the impact of climate change on ginger production and adaptation strategies among farmers in southern part of Kaduna state. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the impact of climate change on ginger production
2. Ascertain the strategies ginger farmers employ toward adapting to climate change

Research questions

1. What are the impacts of climate change on ginger production?
2. What strategies do farmers employ in adapting to climate change?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance

HO₁: A significant difference does not exist in the mean responses of farmers and extension agents on impact of climate change on ginger production in southern parts of Kaduna state.

Methodology

The study was carried out in southern part of Kaduna state, Nigeria. Southern Kaduna state falls within the southern guinea savanna agricultural zone with a favorable climatic conditions for agricultural production. The area is blessed with rich and vast cultivable land that supports the production of most staple crops.

The researcher adopted the survey research design for the study. A survey research design in the view of Chochen, Manion and Marison in Ukonze (2010) is one in which a researcher uses self-completion questionnaire and attitude scale to gather large scale data from representative sample of the population. The design was found appropriate for the study because data were collected systematically from a population sample using a self-constructed questionnaire, analyzed and findings generalized to the entire population. The population for the study was 36,545 consisting of 30 extension agents (E.As) and 36,515 registered ginger farmers in the five (5) extension blocks in Samaru zone of the Kaduna state Agricultural Development Project (ADPs). The extension blocks include Zango, Kafanchan, Kagarko, Kachia and Sanga. The multistage, purposive and random sampling techniques were used to draw 220 ginger farmers used for the study whereas the entire number of E.As was involved. Firstly, two extension cells were purposively selected from each of the five (5) extension blocks (giving a total of 10 extension cells). The criterion was two extension cells in each block with the highest number of ginger farmers. This sampling process produced 2200 farmers at this stage. Further, 10% of the farmers

in the 10 extension cells were randomly selected giving a total of 220 farmers used for the study. Hence, the total sample size for the study was 250.

A questionnaire constructed by the researcher was used for the study. The instrument was designed into two parts, A and B with each addressing a particular research question of the study. Part A, which was responded to by both EAs and ginger farmers had 15 items with four response options of High Impact (HI), Moderate Impact (MI), Low Impact (LI) and No Impact (NI) weighed 4,3,2 and 1 in that order. The Part B of the instrument, which was responded to by only ginger farmers was made up of 20 items each with four response options of High Practice (HP), Moderate Practice (MP), Low Practice (LP) and Not Practiced (NP) weighed 4,3,2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was subjected to face validation by 5 experts for appropriateness to answer the research questions and correctness of items constructions. Observations raised were used to improve the final instrument. The split half technique was adopted in establishing the reliability of the instrument by administering it to a part of the population that was not involved in the study. Data so obtained were analyzed using the Cronbach Alpha method which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82. thus, the instrument was considered reliable for the study. Data collection was carried out through personal contact with the help of two assistants. 250 copies of the questionnaire were administered on the respondents (220 for ginger farmers and 30 for E. As). 201 copies of the instrument administered were retrieved representing 80% return rate.

Descriptive and inferential statistic were used in analyzing the data collected for the study. Mean scores were used in answering research questions while standard deviation was employed to validate the closeness of respondent's responses from the mean and from each other. The t-test statistic was used in testing the hypothesis of the study at 0.05% level of significance. For decision taking on data relating to research questions, a criterion value point of 2.50 was used. To arrived at this criterion value, the average of the mean weights was calculated. Items in part A with mean values equal or greater than 2.50 regarded as "High Impact (HI)" whereas those with mean values lower than this criterion point were regarded as "No Impact (NI)". On the other hand, items in part B with mean values of equal or greater than 2.50 were regarded as "High Practice (HI)" and "Not Practiced (NP)" climate change mitigation strategy by ginger farmers if lower than this criterion value. For decisions relating to the test of the hypothesis of the study, the null hypothesis of no

significance was accepted for any item whose significant value was equal or greater than the alpha level of 0.05 whereas it was rejected if otherwise.

Results

Answers to the research questions and test of hypothesis of the study were presented on tables 1 and 2

Impact of climate change on ginger production in southern parts kaduna state

Data on the impact of climate change on ginger production in southern parts of kaduna state and test of hypothesis are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean, Standard deviation and t-test scores of farmers and extension agents on impact of climate change on ginger production in southern parts of southern kaduna state

s/no	Impact on ginger production	Extension agent			Ginger farmers			T	*Sig
		X ₁	SD ₁	R	X ₂	SD ₂	R		
1	Delayed onset of rains	2.61	0.44	HI	3.01	0.11	HI	1.81	NS
2	Early cessation of rains	2.70	0.75	HI	2.80	0.28	HI	-1.92	S
3	Emergence and spread of pests and diseases	2.52	1.06	HI	2.62	1.50	HI	1.52	NS
4	Early onset of rains	2.70	1.79	HI	2.85	1.90	HI	0.76	NS
5	Increased cost of weed, pests and disease control	2.87	0.56	HI	3.51	0.19	HI	-1.31	S
5	Loss due to flooding	1.70	0.11	NI	2.50	0.48	HI	4.09	NS
6	Reduction in farm yield	2.85	0.95	HI	3.05	0.12	HI	2.01	NS
7	Wilting of crops	2.65	0.76	HI	3.11	1.11	HI	-4.90	S
8	Increased incidences of death of crop due to heat scorching	2.92	1.33	HI	3.85	0.80	HI	-0.99	S
9	Increased labour cost	3.65	0.21	HI	2.77	0.21	HI	2.81	NS
10	Increased cost of production	3.05	0.43	HI	3.15	1.45	HI	-6.70	S
11	Decline in farm profitability	2.77	1.30	HI	2.51	0.73	HI	-1.11	S
12	Increased loss of farm land	3.00	1.09	HI	3.41	0.88	HI	0.32	NS
13	Reduction in quality and market value of produce	3.56	0.21	HI	2.85	0.25	HI	0.40	NS
14	High storage losses due to rising temperatures	2.98	1.11	HI	2.52	0.91	HI	-1.05	S
15	Wilting of crops	3.15	1.09	HI	3.09	1.33	HI	0.28	NS

Key: X₁=Mean of extension agents; SD₁= Standard deviation of extension agents; X₂= Mean of ginger farmers; SD₂=Standard deviation of ginger farmers; HI= High impact; NI= No impact; NS= No significant; S=Significant; R= Remark

Data on table 1 revealed that all the items except 1 (i.e. item 5) were high impact of climate change on ginger production in southern parts of Kaduna state as their mean values ranged from 2.50-3.65 for both extension agents and farmers. It should be noted that the range of mean values

generated from the two groups of respondents is higher than the criterion mean value of 2.50. only item 5 had a mean value less than the criterion value implying that it was considered by both groups of respondents as not being an impact of climate change on ginger production. The same table 1 showed that the Standard deviation (SD) of the 15 items for both extension agents and farmers ranged from 0.11-1.79 indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and to one another in their responses. Further, data on table 1 revealed that there is significant difference in the mean responses of extension agents and ginger farmers on 7 items (items 2,5,7,8,10,11 and 14) and no significant difference in the other 8 items (items 1,3,4,6,9,12,13 and 15). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was rejected for the 7 items whose significant values were less than p-value of 0.05 and upheld the 8 whose significant values were equal or above the p-value.

Climate change adaptation strategies adopted by ginger farmers in southern parts of Kaduna state

Data on climate change adaptation strategies adopted by ginger farmers in southern parts of Kaduna state are presented on table 2

Table 2: Mean, Standard deviation and t-test scores of respondents on climate change adaptation strategies adopted by ginger farmers in 2.51-3.97 Kaduna state

s/no	Adaptation strategy	X	SD	R
1	Early planting	2.90	0.85	HP
2	Planting of early maturing varieties	2.51	1.42	HP
3	Planting disease resistant varieties	3.81	1.90	HP
4	Planting drought resistant varieties	3.70	0.11	HP
5	Use of organic manure	3.85	0.14	HP
6	Use of minimum tillage	3.97	0.79	HP
7	Practicing mulching	3.72	0.91	HP
8	Making of contour bunds	2.95	0.88	HP
9	Cover cropping	3.95	1.45	HP
10	Use of wind breaks/shelter belts	2.78	1.21	HP
11	Proper preservation of planting materials	3.11	0.91	HP
12	Use of chemicals like herbicides and insecticides	3.09	0.05	HP
13	Practicing mixed farming	3.15	0.17	HP
14	Changing of planting dates	2.85	0.19	HP
15	Out migration from climate risk areas	3.08	1.15	HP
16	Increase in the number of weeding of cropped land	3.05	1.06	HP
17	Listening to information about climate change	2.80	1.16	HP
18	Processing of ginger to minimize post-harvest losses	3.92	0.16	HP
19	Changing in timing of land preparation	3.20	0.18	HP
20	Use of recommended planting distance	2.59	0.91	HP

Key: X=Mean; SD= Standard deviation; HP=High practice; R=Remark

Data on table 2 indicate that all the 20 items as responded by ginger farmers were high practices of climate change mitigation strategies employed by farmers of ginger in southern parts of Kaduna state as their means ranged from 2.51-3.97 which is higher than the criterion value of 2.50. the standard deviation of the 20 items as responded to by the farmers ranged from 0.05-1.45, indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and to one another in their responses.

Discussion of Findings

The negative impact of global changing weather events on agriculture and general livelihood of the farming majority in Africa and beyond is assuming a dangerous trend. Southern parts of Kaduna state is not shielded from this life threatening menace. Climate change has manifested itself in the area in the form of delayed onset and early cessation of rains, prolonged dry spells, flooding, increased incidences of pests and diseases among others. Changes in weather events has resulted to more adverse effects crop production and livelihood of farmers, crop processors and marketers. In Table 1, ginger farmers and E.As considered all items except 1 as impacts of climate change on ginger production. Items such as increased cost of labor, increased cost of production and decline in farm profitability shows that farmer are spending more on the farm but getting less from their investment. This is because diminished crop yield means decline in return to production, while increased labor cost contributes to production costs. Findings of this study on impact of climate on ginger production is in line with that of Alkali and Joyce (2020) who conducted a study on coping strategies for climate change adopted by crop farmers for sustainable production in Samaru agricultural zone of Kaduna state. The study by Alkali and Joyce found out that some of the effects of climate change include delayed onset of rains, early onset of rains, diminished crop yield among others. The result of the study on Table 1 also concurs with the findings of Ikehi, et al (2014) Ifeanyieze et al (2016) who stated difficulty and cost of agricultural production with decreasing returns to the farmer. Further, findings of the study presented on Table 1 revealed a significant difference in the mean responses of E.As and farmers on some of the items whereas there was non on some other items. For items whose result show no significant difference, it means there exists no real difference and any observed difference at all is merely due to chance which may have resulted due to error in sampling.

Findings of the study presented on Table 2 revealed that farmers considered all the 20 items as strategies adopted by ginger farmers in adapting to climate change. Items such as planting drought and disease resistant varieties, mixed farming, planting early maturing varieties among others were rated as adaptation to climate change strategies highly practiced. It is obviously true that early planting of crops, mixed farming and migration from climate risk areas could break the cycle and spread of diseases while planting early maturing varieties will ensure the crop against unpredictable cases of early cessation of rains. The findings agree with that of Alkali and Kabirat

(2015) who listed strategies for climate change adaptation as planting of early maturing varieties, planting of disease resistant varieties and planting of drought resistant varieties among others. The result is also in line with the findings of Nzeadibe et al (2012) who outlined strategies of adapting to climate change to include cover cropping, mixed farming, out migration from climate risk areas, planting pest and disease resistant varieties among others.

Conclusion

Climate change has become one of the major existential threats to humanity. It has severely affected animal and crop production including ginger production. Its impact is felt across the globe with southern parts of Kaduna state having its share of the negative consequence. Climate change in the area of study has affected profitable and sustainable crop production resulting in heightened hunger and poverty. In order to live successfully with this menace which seem to have become an unavoidable evil, farmers adopt certain measures such as change of planting dates, changing of timing of land preparation, water storage, protection of water sheds, listening to information about climate change among others.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Ginger production in the areas of study being exclusively rain-fed, it is incumbent on government at all levels to constantly and regularly provide weather forecasting information such as time of onset and cessation of rain, and rainfall regime ahead of time. Such information will help to guide farmers in making plans for the cropping season. This could be done via electronic/print media or through extension service.
2. Government, non-governmental organizations and other development partners should subsidize farm inputs. This need is more critical now more than ever before since the input purchase capacity of farmers is changing occasioned by changing climate.
3. Government, through extension service should sensitize farmers on the need disease resistant, drought resistant and early maturing varieties of ginger.

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